

Producing & sparqling Open and FAIR data with the Geovistory environment

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Context

Digitization of research becomes an increasingly important topic in scientific disciplines. Agencies like SNSF, ANR, and Horizon Europe ask funded research projects to detail how the produced data respond to the FAIR principles, as well as the publication of research data and metadata in public repositories so that it can be found, accessed and reused (see Swiss National Science Foundation, "Open Research Data."; European Commission, "Open Data, Software and Code Guidelines."; ANR, "La science ouverte."). Those requirements are in line with the movement of Open Science that advocates for better accessibility of scientific research (especially publicly funded) so that knowledge is easily shared with scientists (as well as the rest of society), thus improving the quality, efficiency and responsiveness of research (see UNESCO, "UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science."). Open data is one of the pillars of this movement.

Such requirements, as well as the increasing awareness and presence of digitization in many aspects of academia, are putting pressure on researchers, who need to learn and understand the principles and standards of FAIR data and its impact on research data, but also require them to acquire new methods and knowledge, such as data management workflows and best practices.

Technologies of Open Data, such as RDF, also allow the analysis across multiple datasets through complex research queries, which gives researchers the possibility to ask a wider number of questions to their research data. Acquiring

the new technical skills needed to manipulate those technologies would allow researchers to mobilize those new tools and therefore fully benefit from Open Data.

The goal of the Geovistory (<http://geovistory.org>) environment is to alleviate the weight for researchers, by providing tools and practices that are easy to use, help them structure their research data according to the FAIR principles, as well as also allow them to mobilize the full potential of their data for research with digital analysis tools.

About Geovistory

Geovistory is an attractive virtual research and data publication environment designed to strengthen Open Research Data practices. Geovistory is developed for research projects in the humanities and especially in history according to the participatory method of "user experience design". Geovistory supports researchers with simple and easy-to-use interfaces and allows them to make their research accessible in an attractive way to people interested in history. Geovistory includes:

- The Geovistory Toolbox, which allows to manage and curate projects' research data. The Toolbox is freely accessible for all individual projects. Each research project works on its own data perspective but at the same time automatically contributes to a joint knowledge graph.
- The Geovistory Publication platform Geovistory (<http://geovistory.org>), which allows to access data as an external user via the community page or project-specific webpages and its graphical search function or the SPARQL-endpoint.

Fig. 1: Geovistory components.

A particular strength of Geovistory is its handling of the challenges of scientific information in the Humanities and Social Sciences: The context-sensitive nature of information and its relation to different research agendas, the wide variations in meaning for the same terms and vocabulary complexities, competing views or gaps and fragmentation of available information. This is what makes the Geovistory

graph data model and semantic enrichment capabilities so interesting for the Humanities and Social Sciences research.

The data model is collaboratively managed in the ontome.net (<http://ontome.net>) application and takes advantage of the ontology ecosystem of the Semantic Data for Humanities and Social Sciences project (<https://ontome.net/ns/sdhss/>), relying on CIDOC CRM as a high-level ontology. The robust and modular modeling method allows extending the ontology easily and thus using Geovistory as a virtual research environment to researchers in different Humanities and Social Sciences disciplines.

As per current terms of service, all data produced in the information layer of Geovistory are licensed under creative commons BY-SA 4.0. The different infrastructure components are jointly developed by KleioLab, LARHRA, the University of Bern, and welcome other actors joining the Geovistory vision. All the web components and the publication platform have been made available as open source, and before the end of 2023, the toolbox and other components will be made open. The LOD4HSS project (<https://www.geovistory.org/lo4hss>), co-funded by swissuniversities, structures these efforts.

Geovistory within the DH ecosystem

Fig. 2: Geovistory and the FAIR Principles.

First, Geovistory does not predefine the specific data model but rather consumes it via an API from the community-driven ontology management environment OntoMe (see elaborations above), allowing data semantification and community-led interoperability.

Second, the Geovistory ecosystem is connected dynamically to the information systems of producers of authority records (such as IdRef, GND) and other data repositories (such as Wikidata) in view of interconnecting bibliographic information systems and scale up to a large knowledge graph. In this area, a data exchange pipeline has been built with the French Agence Bibliographique de l'Enseignement Supérieur (ABES) and further cooperations are currently being set up.

Third, long-term data storage solutions for projects that concluded active research is important. This can be done in the Zenodo repository. Ideally, cooperation with DaSCH,

OLOS and Huma-Num would be established allowing dynamic updates, with first exchanges with DaSCH underway.

About the Academic Education & Careers project

The project *Academic Education & Careers* (<https://www.geovistory.org/project/1483135>) is a collaborative project enriched by the Geovistory community. This makes this project an ideal showcase of the potential of Geovistory, both in terms of the collaboration philosophy and in terms of data management.

The project *Academic Education & Careers* uses the Geovistory infrastructure and has been initiated at the vDHD (German Digital Humanities Conference) in 2021, as part of a collaborative experiment. In this experiment, the first dataset, the directory of scholars at the University of Kiel in Germany, has been added. It was further enriched with data from the Siprojuris project on French law professors (1804-1950) (<http://siprojuris.symogih.org/>). Siprojuris has been constituted by the career files of law teachers, mainly held by the Archives Nationales and the Centre des Archives Contemporaines de Fontainebleau, as well as civil status records and printed sources, primarily obituaries published in the local, national, or specialist press.

Since then, the project *Academic Education & Careers* has become an open and collaborative **community project** on the history of science and universities. It documents information about professors from different universities and their academic careers, ranging from their graduation to their professorship. The project aims to deepen the understanding of the individual careers of academic professors, enabling researchers to place the intellectual output of these scholars in a broader perspective, comparing social, religious, and political dimensions. By providing bibliographic information to better link the academic world with the trajectories of its actors, the project *Academic Education & Careers* sheds light on the mechanisms behind the production of academic knowledge.

This project is a collaborative endeavor. In other words, it is open and available to all users of Geovistory and has two purposes:

- To allow users to discover Geovistory Public as well as the(?) Geovistory Toolbox, explore the various entities, sources, and texts, and understand how the knowledge graph is structured in the data management tools. Generic pre-written queries are also available to showcase the analysis of temporal and geographical data;
- To encourage users to contribute to the project, either by adding new entities, enriching existing information, or adding new corpora to the knowledge graph.

About the workshop

The workshop is planned as a tutorial based on the community project “Academic Education & Careers” and is open to all participants with an interest in learning about Open Research Data practices within the Geovistory environment. Participants should bring their own laptops. The workshop has two objectives:

- Introduce participants to the principles of FAIR and Open Research Data management, so that participants can understand the usefulness of following those standards, not only for the publication of data and its potential reuse but also for how it can help the researcher throughout the research cycle.
- Give participants a concrete hands-on experience of the Geovistory Research environment (Geovistory Toolbox, Project Webpage, and SPARQL-endpoint) from data production, to publication, to analysis and reuse.

For this, the workshop is structured as follows:

- Introduction to Geovistory and the *Academic Education & Careers* community project: context & history of the project and of the Geovistory platform, experiences & results of the first phase of the project in the first workshop vDHD21 and how the current workshop will build upon it.
- Presentation on the standards and principles of FAIR data, and the general Open Data Research practices, and how it can affect Humanities research data and how researchers can benefit from it.
- Introduction on ontologies for the humanities, with the ICOM standard CIDOC-CRM (ISO 21127:2014), as well as the SDHSS extensions for the Humanities. The goal is to help the participants understand the underlying principles and standards that structure Geovistory and apprehend the semantics behind the data model with the help of examples of the community project. This understanding will be strengthened during the hands-on part of the workshop.
- Hands-on insight into the Geovistory environment, and especially the toolbox, by using sample data from the *Academic Education & Careers* community project, and following the work process of data ingestion, structuration, enrichment, and linking with useful resources (from the Geovistory shared knowledge graph but also external resources, such as the GND, Getty vocabularies, etc.).
- Hands-on introduction on the possibilities of data analysis within the Toolbox, but also on the public project knowledge graph via SPARQL endpoint.
- Open discussion to reflect on the workshop based on the impressions gained and the participant’s own experiences, and on what Geovistory can bring to the participant’s research.

Bibliographie

Swiss National Science Foundation, "Open Research Data." Swiss National Science Foundation. Accessed July 19, 2023. <https://www.snf.ch/en/dMILj9t4LNk8NwyR/topic/open-research-data>

European Commission, "Open Data, Software and Code Guidelines." Open Research Europe. Accessed July 19, 2023. <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/for-authors/data-guidelines#standardsandfair>

ANR, "La science ouverte." Agence nationale de la recherche. Accessed July 19, 2023. <https://anr.fr/fr/lanr/engagements/la-science-ouverte/>

UNESCO, "UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science." UNESCO. Accessed July 19, 2023. <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about?hub=686>